

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Luxmi**FIRST NAME:** Shobha**PROGRAM CODE:** MIPH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2013 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **For writing an essay following is required.**

- Analyze the task.¹**
- Do not plan your essay.
- Do not write an initial draft.
- Do not take notes from your readings.

2. **Which of the following is example of plagiarism?**

- When the author uses a source of information without giving credit to the author.²**
- When the author does not mention the source for information which is common.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: period 1. 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

² Ibid, 5.

- When the author mentions the name of webpage from where the information is taken.
- When the author paraphrases the information and cites the source.

3. **In heading caps, which of the following are capitalized?**

Adjectives.³

- Articles.
- Prepositions.
- Conjunctions.

4. **Which of the following is the correct sequence of the process of writing?**

Prewriting, writing, revising, editing, publishing.⁴

- Prewriting, writing, editing, revising, publishing.
- Prewriting, writing, publishing, editing, revising.
- Prewriting, editing, revising, rewriting, publishing.

5. **Which of the following is the trait of effective writing?**

Logical organization.⁵

- Non stimulating ideas

³ Ibid., 45.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 5.

⁵ Ibid., 20.

- Non engaging voice
- Long sentences

6. **Which of the following rule is correct according to WHO style guide?**

- The format for date is day/month/year.⁶**
- For the geographical regions, use the term western world or underdeveloped countries.
- Use words rather than figures for decades.
- When referring to the “governing bodies” of WHO, use upper-case letters.

7. **When do you need a citation?**

- When you summarize the ideas of others.³**
- When you explain your theories and ideas.
- When surveys and experiments are carried by you.
- When you give information that is common.

8. **In Chicago, bibliography-note style the following is the correct order of elements in footnote.**

⁶ World health organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 7.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4. 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic, 2020), 55.

- Author's first and last name, Title of book: Subtitle of book (Place of publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication, XX).**⁸
- Author's last name and first name, Title of book: Subtitle of book. Place of publication: Publisher's name, Date of Publication, XX.
- Author's first name and last name. Date of Publication. Title of book: Subtitle of book: Place of Publication: Publisher's name, XX.
- Author's last name and first name. Date of Publication. Title of book: Subtitle of book: Place of Publication: Publisher's name, XX.
9. **In Turabian Author-date style, the following is the correct order of elements if there is single author, in reference list entries.**
- Author's last name, Author's first name. Year of Publication. Title of book: Subtitle of book. Place of Publication: Publisher's name.**⁹
- Author's first name, Author's last name. Title of book: Subtitle of book. Year of Publication: Place of Publication: Publisher's name.
- Author's first name, Author's last name. Title of book: Subtitle of book. Place of Publication: Publisher's name. Year of Publication.
- Author's first name, Author's last name. Year of Publication. Title of book: subtitle of book. Publisher's name: Place of Publication.
10. **In Turabian Author's-Date style, if there are more than one authors which is the correct order of mentioning author's name?**

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 91.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 129.

- First author's name inverted; other authors' name is mentioned correct order.**¹⁰
- None of the author's name inverted.
- First author's name in correct order, rest of the author's name inverted.
- All of the authors' names are inverted.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

¹⁰ Ibid., 129.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.